

EFFECTS OF KIDNEY DYSFUNCTION ON DISEASE COURSE IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

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The purpose of the study: to study cardiorenal relationships in patients with CHF.

Material and methods The study included 70 patients with clinical signs of CHF II, III FC according to NYHA of ischemic origin with LV EF $51.9 \pm 6.68\%$. Of these, 39 (56.2%) patients with CHF I FC (LV EF $60.2 \pm 5.09\%$) and 31 (43.8%) patients with CHF III FC (LV EF $47.2 \pm 6.61\%$), mean age was 62.5 ± 7.1 years.

All patients underwent echocardiography in M-mode with a 365 MHz pulse transducer in the position of the patient on the left side. In all patients, the level of creatinine (Cr) was determined and the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) was calculated using the MDRD formula. Depending on the GFR, patients were divided into 2 groups: the first consisted of 21 patients with GFR <60 ml/min/1.73 m², the second - 49 patients with GFR ≥ 60 ml/min/1.73 m². These studies were processed using the STATISTICA 6.0 software package (Statsoft, USA)

Results. GFR was 65.6 ± 19.7 ml/min/1.73 m², and in 24 (33%) patients, GFR was <60 ml/min/1.73 m². In the majority of patients - 46 (68%), the left ventricular ejection fraction was preserved (EF $> 50\%$). Patients with reduced kidney function had a larger left atrial diameter. Mean GFR was 65.6 ± 19.7 ml/min/1.73 m². At the same time, in patients with CHF FC I GFR was 82.3 ± 7.44 ml/min/1.73 m², with CHF FC III 61.8 ± 7.5 ml/min/1.73 m². GFR was lower in patients with AF than without AF (56.6 ± 15.3 versus 68.2 ± 17.6 ml/min/1.73 m², respectively, $p < 0.001$).

However, the average GFR values in terms of creatinine and cystatin C levels are below normal values (83.12 ± 12.78 and 84.25 ± 11.87 ml/min/1.73 m², respectively) and indicate the presence of a decrease in patients. GFR and renal glomerular filtration disorders. A decrease in GFR (mild and moderate), determined by the level of cystatin C, was observed in 63.7% of patients. Consequently, the majority of patients with CHF of ischemic origin had CD

(kidney dysfunction) in the absence of primary renal pathology. A moderate decrease in GFR (as measured by the level of cystatin C) was observed in 6.9% of patients - these patients have target organ damage in the absence of clinical manifestations.

Conclusion. In our study, most patients with CHF of ischemic etiology have signs of in the absence of clinical manifestations. In CHF III FC, signs of CD are determined against the background of endothelial dysfunction and increased arterial stiffness. It is possible that the close relationship of DP with the severity of the clinical condition of patients with CHF partially explains the role of CD as a factor in the progression of CHF, which emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive examination of the kidneys in patients with CHF and the inclusion of methods for assessing renal hemodynamics among the methods for diagnosing CD.

References:

1. Carey R. M., Calhoun D. A., Bakris G. L., Brook R. D., Daugherty S. L., Dennison-Himmelfarb C. R., et al. Resistant Hypertension: Detection, Evaluation, and Management: A Scientific Statement From the American Heart Association // Hypertension. 2018; 72 (5): 53–90. DOI: 10.1161/HYP.0000000000000084.
2. Babu M., Drawz P. Masked Hypertension in CKD: Increased Prevalence and Risk for Cardiovascular and Renal Events // Curr Cardiol Rep. 2019; 21 (7): 58. DOI: 10.1007/s11886-019-1154-4.
3. „Evaluation Of Hypotensive Therapy In Patients With Cardiorenal Syndrome” DOI: 10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S09.578
4. Tursunova Laylo Dilshatovna

